

PORT ORGANIZATION. A UNITARY CONCEPT IN VARIOUS CONTEXTS

Andreea-Maria MOLDOVEANU ¹, Aurel-Mihail ȚÎȚU ²

PhD Student ¹, Prof., PhD ^{2,3}

National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest, Faculty of
Industrial Engineering and Robotics ¹, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu ²

313 Splaiul Independenței, 6th District, Bucharest, Romania ¹,

10 Victoriei Street, Sibiu, Romania ²

andreea.ungureanu1397@gmail.com ¹, mihail.titu@ulbsibiu.ro ²

Abstract

Purpose – proposing a unitary concept for the third component of the port system, analyzing all types of organizations that fall into this category.

Methodology/approach – the categories of existing port organizations were analyzed and how they are found in the specialized literature with the aim of finding a common concept valid for all types.

Findings – there are many types and typologies of organizations that carry out activities in the port field that often have different names or concepts and attributes depending on the area where they are discussed.

Research limitations/implications – given the particularities of each port and region on the globe, it is possible that certain types of organization have not been taken into account by omission.

Practical implications – the use of a unitary concept of port organization could facilitate collaborations between institutions, governing bodies and ports at a global level.

Originality/value – a concept proposal for port organizations that provide port services or carry out activities related to water transport.

Key words: port organization, port management

Introduction

Seaports represent complex systems within global logistics chains with a significant positions in the economic growth of a country open to the sea. Port systems consist of three major components: infrastructure, superstructure and port organizations that operate these structures. This paper proposes a unitary concept for the third component of the port system, analyzing all types of organizations that fall into this category. Proposing a definition for this term is not intended to change or replace certain terms already existing in the literature, but rather to facilitate the use of a unitary and universal concept valid in various contexts. This term refers to a category of organizations, not to the way the port is organized or managed.

The lack of a concrete definition for port organizations is due to a deficiency in the national legislation that appears since the regulation of the terms administration, port operator, authority, port service provider. Because there can be organizations of the type: administration, operator or service provider (safety, pilotage, towing, tying, untying), more precisely, many types and typologies of organizations in the port field, making it difficult to compose a term

whose definition to include all types of existing port organizations. Although certain terms are defined and present in Romanian legislation, there are certain inconsistencies.

The structure of the port system

The global integration of production and consumption, the development of an international transportation network, shifts in relationships between ports, along with dynamics in port hinterlands and logistics, have heightened competition among ports. Carriers, providers and shipping companies no longer simply opt for a particular port; instead, they choose a chain where a port represents a single node. To meet the demands of international trade and supply chains, ports must efficiently handle an increased volume of larger vessels and hinterland modes of transport. These evolving trends, together with the increasing influence of private companies in port operations, are forcing ports to adopt a strategy more market-oriented, innovative and adaptive in order to meet the diverse requirements of all stakeholders engaged in trade passing through ports. (Notteboom, Pallis, and Rodrigue, 2022).

A port is a specialized facility or location where ships and other craft can dock to load and unload cargo, passengers or to carry out various maritime activities. These points has an important position in the context of global trade and transport, acting as nodal points in shipping and transport of persons between land and water transport networks. The size and complexity of ports can vary considerably, from small fishing ports to large international container ports handling millions of containers annually. They are essential components of the global supply chain, facilitating the structured movement of goods and supporting economic growth (European Commission, 2014).

As defined by the law, a port encompasses a designated land and water area, equipped with the necessary infrastructure and facilities for the arrival of ships, the loading and unloading of cargo, storage of goods, as well as the boarding and disembarking of passengers and crew, along with any additional infrastructure required by transport operators within the port. (Ministry of Transport, 2019).

Moreover, the specific structure and organization of a port system can vary greatly relying on factors as size, location and the types of cargo it handles. Some ports may be small and specialized, while others are large and multifaceted, with extensive infrastructure and services (Notteboom, Pallis, and Rodrigue, 2022).

In a more simplistic way, the port considered as a system (Figure 1) has the following components:

- Port infrastructure – according to the law, port infrastructure is defined as the facilities and structures necessary for offering port services in relation to transportation. This includes items such as docking areas for ships, pier walls, quays, pontoons in tidal zones, inland basins, embankments, and land reclaimed from water. Additionally, it involves infrastructure for alternative fuels and systems for the waste collection from the operation of ships and cargo residues. (Ministry of Transport, 2019);
- Port superstructure – structures related to transportation that are supported by various facilities, including storage areas, fixed structures like warehouses and terminal buildings, as well as mobile equipment such as cranes. (Ministry of Transport, 2019);
- Port organizations – these represent organizations that operate in the port field and their object of activity is according to the activities performed within the port or activities related to water transport that impact the development and global performance of the port.

Figure 1. The structure of the port system

A port's infrastructure and superstructure, together with the diverse range of organizations involved, create a complex ecosystem that facilitates the movement of goods and supports traffic and trade. The collaboration and coordination of these elements is crucial for the efficient and effective operation of a port.

Regarding the management model adopted by the ports, it is impacted by a number of elements that determine the optimal management to meet the identified needs. These factors can be: Past developments of the port system, the socio-economic structure of the country, types of goods handled and the port location.

Figure 2 Categories of ports according to the influencing factors on the way of organization

The management approach embraced by the port dictates the management style of the port entities—be it public or private—nestled within its confines. Consequently, private port entities

like port operators function as independent enterprises with unique management and organizational frameworks, while public port entities typically operate under the direction of the port authority, which falls under the jurisdiction and supervision of the Ministry of Transport, and where the workforce comprises civil servants employed by the port authority (Parola et al., 2015).

The intricate nature of port configurations is a significant subject that impacts maritime efficiency through a range of elements such as the extent of relevant operations, the expansion of intermodal transportation, and adverse consequences (Quintano, Mazzocchi, and Rocca, 2020).

Analysis of specific terms and determinants: the concept of port organization

The IMO lists on its official website the port organizations (Maritime Knowledge Centre, n.d.) as agencies, associations, committees or institutions specialized in the port field that practically represent port authorities or administrations, port companies, shipowners as well as decision-makers.

As a port system is composed of infrastructure, superstructure and port organizations, it follows that port organizations must refer to all organizations operating in the port with activities related to water transport or related activities. Thus, to define the term port organization, it is demanded to analyze the determining factors that contribute to its conception. The port organization can refer to a wide range of port actors. The port organization can be represented by a port administration/authority, a port operator or a port service provider (Figure 2).

In quality management, an organization is defined as an individual or a group of individuals that possesses specific functions, responsibilities, authorities, and relationships to achieve its goals. (Anttila, J., & Jussila, K, 2017). Thus, in port field, it can be used the port organization for any entity that respect this definition and also the characteristics of port related activities.

In Regulation (EU) 2017/352, adopted by the European Parliament and the Council on February 15, 2017, which sets forth a framework for port service provision and outlines common financial transparency standards for ports (European Commission, 2017), the European Commission provides definitions for the following terms:

- The term "competent authority" refers to any public or private entity empowered to perform activities associated to the organization and management of port operations, on behalf of an authority at the local, regional, or national level, as defined by domestic laws or national instruments. This includes the port administration or its designated representatives.
- The term "port management authority" refers to any governmental or private entity that, according to national laws or regulations, is designated or authorized to oversee and manage port facilities at the local level. This includes performing various functions, whether independently or in conjunction with other activities, such as coordinating and managing port traffic, as well as overseeing the operations of various stakeholders within the port.
- A "port service provider" is defined as any individual or legal entity that offers or intends to offer one or more types of port services for a fee.
- The term "terminal operator" is not defined by Romanian legislation, but in the framework of the United Nations Convention, it is described as the natural or legal person responsible for taking custody of goods involved in international transport, having the role of guaranteeing the performance of related services relating to goods.

However, we find in the State Aid Scheme of 26.10.2023 the definition: "private port operators" - micro, small, medium or large enterprises settled corresponding to the specific legislation of the member state of which they hold nationality, which carry out unloading and loading activities, transshipment, receipt and dispatch of goods from the ship, to the ship to and from other means of transport (Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure, 2023). (Insert figure 3 about here)

A category of organizations that contribute to the operation and existence of the port is represented by the interested parties. Stakeholders are persons or groups of persons (organizations) that influence the performance of port activities or are influenced by them. They cannot be fully classified as port organizations considering that apart from the economic actors carrying out port/logistics activities what can be port organizations (other loading/unloading organizations, carriers, inspection services, shipping lines, organizations pilotage/towage, other operators, etc.), there are other stakeholders such as: public policy makers, internal stakeholders (directors, employees, members of the Board of Directors, shareholders, etc.) and community groups: local residents, consumers/taxpayers, environmental groups, the media, and others (Notteboom, Pallis, and Rodrigue, 2022).

Thus, we can define the port organization = individual or legal person, public or private entity that:

- Is empowered to perform activities associated to the organization and management of port operations, on behalf of an authority at the local, regional, or national level, as defined by domestic laws or national instruments, or
- is designated or authorized to oversee and manage port facilities at the local level. This includes performing the coordination and management of port traffic, as well as overseeing the operations of various stakeholders within the port, or
- offers or intends to offer one or more types of port services for a fee, or
- according to the specific legislation of the member state whose nationality it holds, carries out activities of unloading, loading, transshipment, receiving and dispatching goods from the ship, to the ship to and from other means of transport.

Conclusion

Given that the types of existing port organizations are extremely different, combining the definitions provided by official sources is almost impossible. Thus, in order to provide a definition of this term, the existing definitions can be cumulated, using the most relevant variant depending on the case. Proposing a definition for this term is not intended to change or replace certain terms already existing in the literature, but rather to facilitate the use of a unitary and universal acceptable concept valid in various contexts. The term would be: port organization, not to be confused with the same expression in English that translates verbatim: "port organization" which refers to the way of organizing the port in question (or port management).

Figure 3 Types of port organizations

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